

Detecting speculation in the market for EU emission allowances[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates whether the price spikes observed in the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) from 2017 to 2022 – a period characterised by rapid price increases and heightened volatility – were driven by speculative episodes, price bubbles, and abnormal trading activity. We apply, for the first time to our knowledge, the bubble detection procedure developed by Phillips and Shi (2020) to futures prices of emission allowances. The approach integrates a right-sided recursive testing algorithm with a bootstrap approach that accounts for heteroscedasticity, as is common in most EU ETS studies, and for family-wise size errors, which can significantly reduce detection power. Additionally, we use an abnormal trading detection method to identify unusual patterns in both futures and options markets. Our findings reveal seven speculative bubbles, spanning 154 out of 1,521 trading days, or approximately 10% of the sample period. We also identify ten instances of abnormal trading in futures and twelve in options, with four aligning with detected speculative bubbles. By examining 69 regulatory events related to the EU ETS during the period studied, we observe that six of the seven bubbles correspond with regulatory announcements. These results demonstrate that speculative activity has substantially influenced emission allowances prices, causing significant deviations from their fundamental values. This highlights the importance of continuously monitoring speculative impacts within the EU ETS and underscores the need for careful timing and communication of regulatory interventions.

1. Introduction

The European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) is the world's first large-scale CO₂ emissions trading system and a central pillar of the EU's strategy to achieve a net-zero greenhouse gas economy by 2050. Established in 2005, the EU ETS sets a progressively declining emission cap and allows compliance entities and financial actors to trade European Union Allowances (EUAs), which serve as permits to emit CO₂. The economic rationale behind the EU ETS is that emissions trading allows the overall economy to achieve emissions reduction in a cost-effective manner (Montgomery, 1972; Rubin, 1996). However, the efficiency and effectiveness of the system depend on the permit price being 'right', i.e. accurately reflecting the marginal abatement cost.

EUA prices have been characterised by very diverse dynamics over the years. In the early phases of the ETS, prices remained low, partly due to an oversupply of allowances.¹ However, since 2017, EUA prices have experienced a sharp upward trend, rising from below €10 per tonne of CO₂ to over €90 by the end of 2022.² This price increase is partly attributed to significant reforms introduced in 2018 that aimed to align the EU ETS with the EU's 2050 net-zero goals, including the introduction of the Market Stability Reserve (MSR), a mechanism designed to adjust allowance supply annually to stabilise prices and prevent extreme fluctuations (Neuhoff et al., 2015).

While, as outlined in the literature review later in this section, fundamentals and regulatory factors have also played a role in shaping permit price dynamics, the rapid rise in prices and volatility have raised concerns about the influence of speculation. Since 2018, participation

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¹ Since 2008, the annual issuance of EUAs has generally exceeded demand, leading to a cumulative surplus of 2.1 billion tonnes by the start of Phase III and a record low price of €2.81 in January 2013.

² More recently, since the beginning of 2023, prices have fallen between 60 and 70 euros per tonne.

by financial actors has surged (Quemin and Pahle, 2022), with the number of investment funds more than tripling and their share relative to intermediaries expanding significantly (Roques et al., 2022). While some speculative trading can enhance liquidity and support price discovery, excessive speculation risks driving volatility, market manipulation, and inefficient pricing, potentially creating bubbles that divert prices from their fundamental values. Despite increased attention to the role of speculation in the EU ETS, limited research examines its impact on EUA prices, especially in recent years. Understanding whether recent price spikes stem from speculative bubbles or market fundamentals is critical for clarifying the drivers of price formation and determining whether further regulatory adjustments are necessary.

This paper addresses this gap by analysing speculative activity in the EUA market from 2017 to 2022, a period marked by significant price increases and growing concerns around speculation. Our research focuses on three main questions. Firstly, were the price volatility and spikes from 2017 to 2022 driven by speculative bubbles or fundamental factors, and to what extent do our results on this differ from previous studies? Secondly and relatedly, was there abnormal trading activity in this period in the markets for EUA futures and options and did this coincide with periods of high speculative activity? Thirdly, did detected periods of price exuberance coincide with regulatory announcements or policy changes?

To address these questions, we apply the real-time bubble detection procedure developed by Phillips and Shi (2020) (hereinafter PS) to daily EUA futures prices from the Intercontinental Exchange (ICE) over the 2017–2022 period.³ To our knowledge, this study represents the first use of the PS procedure on EUA prices. PS is a real-time bubble detection procedure that utilises a recursive testing algorithm to identify speculative bubbles and to date their origin and termination. It refines the procedure introduced in Phillips et al. (2015) (PSY), which in turn builds on Phillips and Yu (2011) (PY) and Phillips et al. (2011) (PWY), by incorporating a wild bootstrap technique to address both heteroscedasticity and family-wise size – an issue typically unaddressed in applications of PSY. The PSY framework has been widely employed across various financial domains, including the EU ETS (e.g., Cretí and Joëts, 2017; Friedrich et al., 2020), where it is often paired with wild bootstrapping methods focused on correcting heteroscedasticity alone (Gonçalves and Kilian, 2004). However, as shown by Shi et al. (2020), controlling solely for heteroscedasticity is insufficient; recursive testing algorithms also face the challenge of family-wise size, which can significantly weaken the detection power of PSY. The PS methodology addresses this by combining PSY with a wild bootstrap procedure including two components: the heteroscedasticity control method by Harvey et al. (2016) and the procedure developed in Shi et al. (2020) to control family-wise size. This wild bootstrap increases the robustness and detection power of PSY, establishing it as a valuable early warning tool across a range of asset classes.

In addition to detecting speculative bubbles, we identify abnormal trading activity patterns in EUA futures and options, the latter of which has not yet been studied (Quemin and Pahle, 2022). To this end, we apply an abnormal trading activity detection method to both ICE EUA futures and EEX EUA options data. Originally developed by Chesney et al. (2015) for options, this method identifies abnormal trading patterns based on open interest, trading volume, and returns, especially in anticipation of significant events. Given the absence of granular trade-level data, we adapt this method to account for the lack of individual hedging information.

Finally, we compile a list of 69 regulatory events related to the EU ETS for the period 2017–2022 from two sources. We first extend the regulatory events list from the Climate Action news archive, provided by Känzig (2023) and subsequently expanded by Hengge et al. (2023),

resulting in 47 events. Additionally, we include 22 regulatory events from the Official Journal of the European Union,⁴ following the approach of Fan et al. (2017). This list of regulatory events allows us to qualitatively assess whether periods of price exuberance align with policy announcements or regulatory changes.

Our findings reveal seven speculative bubbles in EUA futures, with an average duration of 22 days, covering approximately 154 days out of a total sample of 1521 trading days, indicating that over 10% of trading days show price deviations from fundamental values. This provides significant evidence of speculation influencing EU ETS prices, with the longest bubbles lasting 60 days at the end of 2021 into early 2022, a period marked by rising geopolitical tensions. Moreover, six of the seven speculative bubbles occurred close to regulatory events. Concerning abnormal trading activity, although data limitations prevent us from assessing whether such activity was intended for hedging rather than speculation, we observe ten periods of abnormal trading in EUA futures, with an average duration of 9.6 days, four of which align closely with the speculative bubbles identified. Despite its lower liquidity outside of 2018, we identify twelve periods of abnormal trading in the options market.

This paper contributes to the literature on the functioning of carbon markets and, more specifically, on the role of speculation within the EU ETS. The literature on carbon price formation examines both non-financial and financial determinants of the carbon price. The non-financial factors are typically organised around two main categories: demand-side fundamentals – related to marginal abatement costs – and supply-side forces, which are largely shaped by political and regulatory interventions (Friedrich et al., 2020). A third, increasingly important perspective treats the EU ETS as a financial market, focusing on speculative and hedging behaviour.

On the demand side, a substantial body of work investigates how fuel prices, electricity generation, and macroeconomic activity influence EUA prices. Early studies (e.g., Remes et al., 2013; Koch et al., 2014) highlight that gas prices and economic activity tend to push carbon prices upward, while results regarding coal and other variables are more ambiguous and highly sensitive to methodological choices and sample periods. More advanced contributions – such as those by Lutz et al. (2013) and Cretí et al. (2012) – employ models that allow for regime-switching and non-linear relationships, uncovering the instability of the long-run relationship between fundamentals and EUA prices. Lovcha et al. (2022) provide evidence that the explanatory power of fundamentals has strengthened over time, although the relative influence of specific drivers such as oil, coal, and gas has varied considerably. Batten et al. (2021) examine the role of weather and energy prices, finding that while energy prices explain part of the carbon price variation in Phase III, their explanatory power is modest (around 12%). Interestingly, temperature levels do not influence prices directly, but unexpected temperature fluctuations do. A non-parametric approach is adopted in Salvagnin et al. (2024) to trace the changing importance of price determinants across ETS phases. While in Phase III commodity-related fundamentals were the most informative, financial variables – especially exchange rate movements such as the EUR/CHF – became the predominant drivers in Phase IV.

On the supply side, regulatory uncertainty and political events have been recognised as triggers of price shifts. These shocks are often modelled as probabilistic jumps affecting expected price paths. Event studies, including those by Hitzemann et al. (2015) and Koch et al. (2016), demonstrate that policy announcements related to back-loading and cap adjustments induce significant price volatility and abnormal trading volumes. Deeney et al. (2016) find that European Parliament announcements – particularly those unrelated to party politics – cause negative abnormal returns and heightened volatility. This effect is magnified under low market sentiment or limited news coverage,

³ EUA futures represent the most liquid segment of EUA trading (Cretí and Joëts, 2017; Quemin and Pahle, 2022).

⁴ Available at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/oj/direct-access.html>.

whereas under high market attention, announcements tend to stabilise volatility. Fan et al. (2017) find that nearly half of the regulatory announcements they assess lead to abnormal returns, while Cretí and Joëts (2017) link short-lived price exuberance to identifiable policy episodes, even though such events do not always generate statistically significant returns.

Our paper contributes to this growing literature by investigating the role of speculative activity on the EU ETS price. In particular, we investigate the futures and options segments of the EU ETS to detect episodes of explosive dynamics and patterns of abnormal trading activity. While the literature on carbon derivatives markets remains limited, understanding their role is crucial for assessing the influence of financial speculation on carbon price formation. Previous studies, such as those by Cretí and Joëts (2017), Friedrich et al. (2020), Wei et al. (2022), and Huang and Wang (2024), have applied the PSY procedure to detect speculative bubbles in the EU ETS. Cretí and Joëts (2017) pioneered the use of this method, combined with the wild bootstrap technique of Gonçalves and Kilian (2004) addressing heteroscedasticity, to detect speculative bubbles in EUA prices from 2005 to 2014. Their findings revealed eleven episodes of mild price explosiveness associated with regulatory announcements, indicating that policy uncertainty could spur speculation. Extending this analysis, Friedrich et al. (2020) applied the PSY procedure and other econometric methods to weekly data from 2008 to 2018, finding a prolonged period of explosive behaviour beginning in March 2018, following the adoption of the EU ETS reform. Considering also emission trading systems outside the EU, Wei et al. (2022) analysed bubbles in the EU ETS as well as in New Zealand, South Korea, and Shenzhen from their inception until August 2019, observing that bubbles in the EU, New Zealand, and South Korea persisted for extended periods, often exceeding five days, while Shenzhen's bubbles were shorter-lived. The EU ETS appeared particularly vulnerable to price bubbles, attributed to its sensitivity to industrial shifts and regulatory changes in participating countries. Huang and Wang (2024) applied the SADF and GSADF tests alongside the log-periodic power law singularity model to compare the EU ETS with the systems in New Zealand, California-Quebec, South Korea, China, and the United Kingdom. Their findings indicate that the EU ETS showed the highest frequency of bubbles, while the New Zealand ETS exhibited the longest durations. Bubble activity notably increased in 2021 and 2022, likely influenced by post-COVID-19 economic recovery and geopolitical tensions. These studies, however, apply the PSY procedure without controlling for family-wise error, potentially reducing detection power. An alternative approach is adopted by Wegener et al. (2024), who utilise market expectations rather than fundamental price drivers. They argue that although EUA prices displayed explosive phases, these dynamics were mirrored in market expectations, thereby challenging the interpretation of these phases as speculative bubbles.

We contribute to this literature by applying, for the first time to our knowledge, the PS procedure to detect speculative bubbles in EUA prices over the highly volatile period from 2017 to 2022. In contrast to previous studies, our approach improves the reliability of bubble detection by implementing a wild bootstrap procedure and explicitly correcting for multiple testing, thereby reducing the likelihood of false positives. Our sample partially overlaps with that of Wei et al. (2022). While we do not detect bubbles in 2017 as they do – likely due to the absence of earlier historical data – we identify a greater number of shorter-lived and temporally distinct episodes during the overlapping period. A similar pattern emerges when comparing our results with those of Huang and Wang (2024), whose GSADF-based analysis covers a similar time frame. The bubbles we identify differ both in timing and duration: we detect more short-lived episodes, while their analysis reports longer and more persistent phases, some of which are not confirmed in our results. These discrepancies are plausibly driven by our enhanced methodological framework.

Beyond the existing literature, we extend the analysis by applying an abnormal trading activity detection approach in the carbon derivatives market, applied to both EUA futures and the underexplored segment of EUA options. We further complement the quantitative analysis with a qualitative assessment of the temporal correspondence between speculative episodes and regulatory events. Our findings reveal that EUA prices have been characterised by a succession of short-lived speculative bubbles. This highlights the importance of continuous market monitoring to detect and mitigate speculative pressures. Moreover, the observed alignment between several bubble episodes and regulatory announcements underscores the need for careful policy timing and communication to avoid triggering destabilising speculative responses.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the data, followed by a discussion of the methodology for detecting speculative bubbles and abnormal trading activity in Section 3. Section 4 reports the results, and Section 5 concludes the study. Appendix A.1 illustrates a robustness analysis where results from the PS procedure under alternative parameter settings are outlined. Appendix A.2 provides the list of regulatory events used to investigate the drivers of speculative episodes.

2. Data

In this section, we present the EUA futures and options datasets used for the analysis, as well as some first descriptive statistics and general features of both datasets. We also present the time series of the fundamental drivers of the EUA price.

2.1. EUA futures

Our dataset comprises daily observations of EUA futures prices, returns, trading volumes, and open interest from January 3, 2017, to November 18, 2022 ($T \approx 1521$). This period covers the final years of Phase 3 and the beginning of Phase 4 of the EU ETS and spans significant price surges, which raised concerns about speculative activities in the EU ETS. For real-time monitoring of potential price bubbles, we also analyse shorter subsamples over annual, biannual, and triennial periods ($T \approx 250, 500$, and 750 , respectively).⁵

The EUA price time series is based on front-December EUA futures prices from the Intercontinental Exchange (ICE), selected due to their high liquidity. December-maturity contracts account for an average of 96% of trading volume from 2008 to 2021, with December Y contracts capturing 75% of annual trades on average, compared to lower volumes for contracts maturing in December $Y + 1$, $Y + 2$, and $Y + 3$ (Quemin and Pahle, 2022). We construct the front-December time series using the open interest (OI) switch method, rolling the front contract to the back contract when the back contract's OI surpasses that of the front. This approach maintains liquidity in the constructed time series, as presented in Fig. 1.

Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) present the log-returns distribution and the time series of returns, respectively, for 2017–2022. The summary statistics are provided in Table 1. The log returns exhibit a distribution characterised by a negative skewness (-0.518) and high kurtosis (7.41), indicating a left-tailed and leptokurtic shape, which deviates from the Normal distribution. The negative skewness implies that investors may experience frequent small gains but face occasional large losses, contrasting with the lottery-like distribution often associated with positive skewness, where a high probability of small losses is offset by the chance of large gains. This characteristic might reduce the attractiveness of EUA futures for speculative traders seeking lottery-like payoffs,

⁵ While the power of the real-time monitoring procedure is validated for monthly samples of 100 observations or more (Phillips et al., 2015), daily samples should also suffice for detecting explosive price episodes, as recommended by Etienne et al. (2014).

Fig. 1. ICE EUA December futures prices in the period 2017–2022.

(a) Distribution of EUA December Futures log-returns

(b) Time series of EUA December Futures log-returns

Fig. 2. EUA December futures log-returns in the period 2017–2022.

Table 1
Summary statistics for EUA December futures log-returns.

Statistic	Value
Mean	0.00170
Standard deviation	0.0298
Skewness	-0.518
Kurtosis	7.41

as assets with high positive skewness are usually considered more appealing to speculators willing to bear some risks for the possibility of large gains (e.g. Kumar, 2009). The historical volatility of the log-returns – measured as the average deviation of the returns from the mean over the specified period – is 2.98%, which is roughly in line with other commodities such as oil (2.1%) and gas (4.4%).⁶

Fig. 3 illustrates the Scalping index of the EUA futures during Phase III of the EU ETS. Scalping is the practice of engaging in rapid

⁶ Studies in behavioural finance, such as Dorn and Huberman (2010), suggest that investors are often drawn to highly volatile assets. Algieri and Leccadito (2019) find a strong relationship between volatility and speculation in energy markets, with high volatility contributing to excessive speculative activity.

intraday transactions, where traders open and close positions within a short time frame to capture small profits. This type of trading is typically considered speculative because it is not driven by long-term fundamentals but by short-term price movements. The scalping index is calculated as the ratio of daily trading volume to open interest:

$$Sc_t = \frac{V_t}{OI_t}, \tag{1}$$

where V_t denotes the daily trading volume and OI_t represents the open interest on day t . A high scalping ratio indicates that a significant portion of trading activity is oriented towards short-term gains, which can indicate increased speculative behaviour. The EUA futures Scalping index exhibits an oscillatory pattern with increased noise and an increasing mean, suggesting a rise in short-term speculative trading activity.⁷

⁷ The Working T-index is another measure designed to quantify the extent of speculation by assessing how much open positions exceed levels anticipated from hedging and market-making activities. Previous studies, including Quemin and Pahlé (2022), have observed a marked increase in the Working T-index, with excess speculation rising from 50% to 90% of total hedging volumes between early 2018 and early 2020, and stabilising at levels fluctuating between 70% and 90% thereafter.

Fig. 3. Scalping index S_c , in the period 2017–2022.

Fig. 4. EEX EUA December futures prices in the period 2017–2022.

2.2. EUA options

We also collect data on EUA options – daily prices, open interests, and trading volumes – for the 2017–2022 period. Data is sourced from the European Energy Exchange (EEX), which exclusively trades European call and put options (OEUA) on EUA futures (see Fig. 4 for the EUA future prices on EEX).

Each option's underlying asset is the EUA December Futures contract maturing in the same year as the option. The options dataset is aggregated monthly or yearly. We disaggregate it into individual datasets for each option, categorised by type (call or put), maturity, and strike price. We exclude those options that remained inactive throughout the entire period (i.e., $OI_t = 0$ for all t). Fig. 5 provides an overview of the active call and put options contracts, with the maturity date on the x -axis and strike price on the y -axis.

The options market witnessed substantial growth in 2018, with the number of open contracts surging to 49 calls and 41 puts, mostly expiring in December. This increase was followed by a contraction in subsequent years, with open contracts steadily declining until only a single call option remained in 2022, although the ICE exchange gained more relevance.

Fig. 6 compares the evolution of daily total open interest in option contracts (solid lines) and front-December futures (dashed lines) across different maturities. Open interest in EUA futures increases notably from the December 2017 to the December 2018 contracts and then

stabilises at a higher level. In the options segment, as in the futures market, December emerges as the most liquid maturity. However, the dynamics of open interest differ markedly between the two. While the December 2018 options maturity shows a pronounced rise, coinciding with the first major rally in underlying futures prices (Fig. 4), later maturities fail to sustain comparable levels of open interest, aside from a few transient spikes in the March 2021 contracts. This divergence underscores the distinct market roles of futures and options in the EUA market: futures exhibit a sustained high liquidity, whereas the options market appears more episodic, with activity concentrated in specific periods.

2.3. Fundamental EUA price drivers

The identification of speculative bubbles relies on the general asset pricing equation, which decomposes asset prices into fundamental and bubble components (see Section 3). To apply this framework to EUA futures, we must first define the fundamental drivers of EUA prices.

The literature has proposed several approaches to identifying these drivers. Rubin (1996) developed a theoretical model suggesting that the price of allowances is determined by abatement costs, regulatory limits, and time-preference factors. Instead, empirical studies have highlighted the impact of energy prices and economic activity on EUA prices. Natural gas and coal prices are particularly influential due to their roles in electricity generation – one of the sectors mostly regulated by

Fig. 5. EEX European call and put options on EUA futures. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Daily total open interest for EEX EUA option contracts (solid lines) and front-December futures (dashed lines). Colours represent different maturities. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the ETS. Higher gas prices increase abatement costs, exerting upward pressure on EUA prices, while higher coal prices reduce these costs, pushing EUA prices down. Economic activity also affects EUA prices, as increased production generally leads to higher emissions, raising marginal abatement costs and thereby driving up allowance prices.

Among empirical studies, Koch et al. (2014) identified gas prices and economic activity as significant drivers of EUA prices, whereas coal prices showed no effect. In contrast, Rickels et al. (2015) found that the impact of fuel-switching prices and economic activity was positive, while renewable energy had a limited role. Remes et al. (2013) reported a positive relationship between electricity and carbon prices, along with significant effects from coal and gas prices, aligning with economic theory.

Alternative empirical approaches addressing time variation, non-linearity, and instability have also been explored. For instance, Lutz et al. (2013) distinguished between pricing regimes, identifying coal, gas, oil, and stock indices as determinants of EUA prices, though coal exhibited a counterintuitive effect during high volatility. Cretí et al. (2012) confirmed the significance of these variables through cointegration techniques, showing them to be long-term determinants of EUA prices. More recently, Lovcha et al. (2022) applied a structural

vector autoregression (SVAR) model to link energy prices, economic activity, and carbon prices, finding that the influence of these drivers has evolved over time, with oil and coal gaining prominence over gas and economic activity.

Following the literature, we consider natural gas and oil prices, the coal-to-gas switching price, and economic activity indicators as fundamental determinants of EUA prices. Specifically, we adopt the approach of Cretí and Joëts (2017), who used a simple linear regression model to derive the fundamental component U_t , expressed as:

$$U_t = 0.520 \text{ gas}_t + 0.632 \text{ oil}_t + 0.514 \text{ switch}_t - 0.260 \text{ stock}_t \quad (2)$$

In this equation, gas_t represents natural gas prices, oil_t denotes oil prices, switch_t is the switching price associated with substituting coal (a more carbon-intensive fuel) with natural gas (a cleaner alternative), and stock_t is a stock index reflecting overall economic activity. The switching price switch_t is defined as $\text{switch}_t = 2 \cdot (0.5 \text{ gas}_t - 0.36 \text{ coal}_t)$, with the coefficients calibrated to capture the abatement costs of fuel substitution. This model was empirically validated using data from a stable period in the EUA market, from 27 April 2005 to 5 February 2014, when prices were low and stable, and speculative activity was minimal.

Fig. 7. Fundamental drivers of EUA prices in the period 2017–2022.

We construct the time series of the fundamental drivers using the front December futures prices for consistency, employing ICE data for Natural Gas, Brent Oil, and Rotterdam Coal futures, and the EUR STOXX 50 index. Figs. 7(a) through 7(d) present these time series.

We now examine the properties of the fundamental component U_t in Eq. (2) to ensure the validity of real-time monitoring for detecting speculative bubbles in EUA futures prices. An assumption for applying this monitoring procedure is that the unobserved fundamentals variable U_t is either an $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ process. In other words, U_t must be stationary (exhibiting no stochastic trend) or become stationary after differencing (containing a single unit root). To test the $I(1)$ assumption, we perform an Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test on the differenced series, ΔU_t . The test yields a Dickey–Fuller statistic of -3.2656 with a p -value of 0.0683 , allowing us to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root at the 90% confidence level. This outcome confirms that ΔU_t is stationary, implying that U_t is indeed an $I(1)$ process.

3. Methodology

This section outlines the methodology used to analyse the EUA futures and options markets. First, we describe the real-time monitoring approach, which, to the best of our knowledge, is applied here for the first time to EUA futures prices to test for bubbles. Next, we illustrate the abnormal trading activity detection approach, which enables us to identify periods of unusual trading behaviour. We apply this approach to both EUA futures and options markets, marking the first in-depth exploration of EUA options trading, to our knowledge, in this paper.

3.1. Real-time monitoring

We begin with the general asset pricing equation:

$$P_t = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{1+r} \right)^i \mathbb{E}_t(D_{t+i} + U_{t+i}) + B_t, \tag{3}$$

where P_t denotes the after-dividend price of the asset at time t , \mathbb{E}_t represents the conditional expectation based on the information set available at t , r is the positive discount rate, D_t stands for the dividend, U_t is the fundamental component, and B_t denotes the bubble component, with $t = 1, \dots, T$. To adapt Eq. (3) for EUAs, which do not involve dividend payments, we set the dividend term to zero.

In this framework, if the bubble component B_t is zero, the stochastic trending behaviour of the EUA price process equals that of the fundamental component U_t . However, when B_t is positive, the price exceeds the fundamental value (for $B_t > 0$), and the price process exhibits explosive behaviour, as the bubble component satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}_t(B_{t+1}) = (1+r)B_t, \tag{4}$$

where B_t follows a submartingale process (see Diba and Grossman, 1988).

This framework provides a testable econometric framework for which various methodologies exist. We adopt the approach proposed by Phillips and Shi (2020), which is grounded in a series of studies (Phillips and Yu, 2011; Phillips et al., 2011, 2015) that have significantly advanced the identification of speculative bubbles and their origination and termination dates. The ability to detect the timing of the bubbles is important, given that the start and end points of a bubble process are typically unknown. This methodology combines a recursive testing algorithm with a bootstrapping procedure designed to address the impact of heteroscedasticity and the increased probability

of false positives associated with multiple testing, thereby enhancing the reliability of bubble detection. More specifically, the recursive evolving algorithm by Phillips and Shi (2020) performs Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) tests (Dickey and Fuller, 1979) on subsamples of varying lengths and different starting and ending points.

To perform the ADF tests, the fundamental component must be an integrated process of order zero ($I(0)$) or one ($I(1)$). If this condition is satisfied, any observed explosive behaviour in the price series P_t cannot be attributed solely to the fundamental, suggesting the presence of factors beyond those captured by U_t . As we show in Section 2.3, the fundamental component U_t that we consider is an $I(1)$ process.

The regression equation for the ADF test is:

$$\Delta y_t = \mu + \rho y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \phi_i \Delta y_{t-i} + v_t, \tag{5}$$

where y_t is the observed price time series, Δy_t represents its first difference, μ is a constant, ρ is the coefficient of the lagged level y_{t-1} , and the terms Δy_{t-i} capture lagged differences to account for potential serial correlation in Δy_t . The error term v_t is assumed to be independently and identically distributed, following a normal distribution with zero mean and variance σ^2 . To account for autocorrelation in the residuals, we set the number of lag terms, k , to 6, based on the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) (Phillips et al., 2015).

The objective of the ADF test is to distinguish between the null hypothesis, H_0 , of the price following a random walk process (potentially with drift) and the alternative hypothesis, H_1 , indicating the presence of explosive behaviour in the price series:

$$H_0 : \mu = dT^{-\eta}, \quad \rho = 0, \tag{6}$$

$$H_1 : \mu = 0, \quad \rho > 0, \tag{7}$$

where T is the sample size, and d and $\eta > 1/2$ are constants. The term $dT^{-\eta}$ accounts for any mild drift in the process, which becomes asymptotically negligible. The difference between the null and alternative hypotheses can be further illustrated by reformulating the models as:

$$H_0 : y_t = dT^{-\eta} + y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t, \tag{8}$$

$$H_1 : y_t = \delta_T y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t, \tag{9}$$

where ε_t is a white noise error term, and $\delta_T = 1 + cT^{-\theta}$, with $c > 0$ and $\theta \in (0, 1)$. The specification of the null hypothesis in Eq. (8) and the augmented regression in Eq. (5) are essential for deriving the asymptotic properties and critical values of the ADF statistic.

The ADF t -ratio for the least squares estimate of the coefficient ρ is computed using a backwards-expanding sample sequence, with subsamples defined by varying starting and ending points expressed as fractions of the total sample size T . The window size of each subsample is denoted by $r_w \in [r_0, 1]$, where r_0 represents the minimum window width, and 1 denotes the full sample size. The start and end points of each subsample are given by r_1 and r_2 , respectively. At each step, the endpoint r_2 is fixed, while the starting point r_1 varies within the interval from 0 to $r_2 - r_0$. The minimum window size is set as $\tau_0 = Tr_0$. Following the rule of thumb proposed by Phillips et al. (2015), r_0 is set to $r_0 = 0.01 + 1.8/\sqrt{T}$, balancing the need for a sufficiently large initial subsample for robust statistical inference with the flexibility required for recursive testing.

For each rolling window regression conducted from the r_1 th to the r_2 th fraction of the total time sample, the ADF t -ratio for the estimated coefficient $\hat{\rho}_{r_1, r_2}$ is denoted by $ADF_{r_1, r_2}^{r_2}$:

$$\Delta y_t = \hat{\mu}_{r_1, r_2} + \hat{\rho}_{r_1, r_2} y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \hat{\phi}_{r_1, r_2}^i \Delta y_{t-i} + \hat{v}_t, \tag{10}$$

where \hat{v}_t represents the regression residuals.

The test statistic, known as the backward sup ADF (BSADF) statistic, is the supremum over the sequence of ADF t -ratios:

$$BSADF_{r_2}(r_0) = \sup_{r_1 \in [0, r_2 - r_0]} \{ADF_{r_1}^{r_2}\}. \tag{11}$$

This test generates a sequence of BSADF statistics, which allows the identification of explosive behaviour at specific points. Bubble episodes are identified when the BSADF statistic surpasses its critical value. The start date of a bubble, denoted $T\hat{r}_e$, is the first observation where this criterion is met. The end date, $T\hat{r}_f$, is defined as the first observation occurring after $T\hat{r}_e + \delta \log(T)$, where the statistic falls below the critical threshold. Here, $\delta \log(T)$ establishes the minimum duration required to classify an episode as a bubble. As a consequence, r_2 spans from \hat{r}_e to 1, without additional constraints. The origination and termination dates in fractional form are determined by

$$\hat{r}_e = \inf_{r_2 \in [r_0, 1]} \left\{ r_2 : BSADF_{r_2}(r_0) > cv_{r_2}^\beta \right\}, \tag{12}$$

$$\hat{r}_f = \inf_{r_2 \in [\hat{r}_e + \delta \log(T)/T, 1]} \left\{ r_2 : BSADF_{r_2}(r_0) < cv_{r_2}^\beta \right\}, \tag{13}$$

where $cv_{r_2}^\beta$ denotes the critical value of the BSADF statistic at a significance level β , which we set at 0.05.⁸ Further, following Phillips et al. (2011) and Etienne et al. (2014), which study datasets of comparable frequencies, we set δ to one, ensuring that only episodes longer than $\log(T)$ are included in the analysis.

The calculation of critical values for the test employs a wild bootstrap procedure developed by Phillips and Shi (2020), which consists of two main components. The first, introduced by Harvey et al. (2016), mitigates challenges associated with non-stationary volatility in asset prices, which can elevate the probability of falsely detecting explosive behaviour. This bootstrap procedure allows to conduct the test while preserving its power in finite samples. Although initially developed for the PWY test (Phillips et al., 2011), its principles extend naturally to the PSY procedure, where similar distortions may occur due to non-stationary volatility. The second component, proposed by Shi et al. (2020), addresses the multiple hypothesis testing problem, which emerges when PSY is applied to a series of sequential tests. The likelihood of Type I errors increases as the number of tested hypotheses is high. For a time series of length T , the PSY dating algorithm evaluates $T - Tr_0 + 1$ hypotheses, necessitating a method to control the family-wise error rate across these tests.

The wild bootstrap procedure involves five steps. The second step primarily addresses non-stationary volatility by resampling residuals. The remaining steps mitigate the elevated risk of false positives associated with multiple testing, thereby enhancing the robustness of the PSY procedure in reliably detecting bubbles.

1. The parameters of the regression model, as specified in Eq. (5), are estimated under the null hypothesis H_0 , where the coefficient ρ is set to zero. From this estimation, the residuals e_t are obtained.
2. The initial values are set as $y_j^b = y_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, i$, and the bootstrap sample is constructed with size $\tau_0 + \tau_b - 1$, where $\tau_0 = Tr_0$ represents the smallest window size, and τ_b defines the number of observations over which the test size is controlled. We set $\tau_b = 48$ and perform robustness checks as detailed in Appendix A.1.⁹

⁸ Phillips and Shi (2020) choose to let β depend on T , such that for $T \rightarrow \infty$, $\beta \rightarrow 0$. This ensures that as the sample size grows, the Type I error likelihood goes to zero.

⁹ In Phillips et al. (2018), the authors apply the bootstrap procedure to the S&P index with parameters $T = 537$, $\tau_0 = 47$, and $\tau_b = 24$, thus using a ratio of τ_0 to τ_b of approximately 2 : 1, which we roughly follow.

Table 2

Parameter selection for the PS procedure based on dataset size.

Sample size	Min. wind. size	Min. bubble length	Size control wind. length
1521	85	7	48

Table 3

Parameter selection for the PS procedure independent of dataset size.

Max. N. of lag terms	Conf. lev.	Bootstrap Sim.	Model selection criterion
6	95%	499	BIC

The bootstrap sample is generated using

$$\Delta y_t^b = \sum_{i=1}^k \hat{\phi}_i \Delta y_{t-i}^b + e_t^b, \quad (14)$$

where $\hat{\phi}_i$ are the estimated regression coefficients under the null hypothesis, and $e_t^b = w_t e_t$, with w_t drawn from a standard normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and e_t sampled randomly with replacement from the residuals e_t .

3. The sequence of BSADF test statistics, $\{BSADF_t^b\}_{t=\tau_0}^{\tau_0+\tau_b-1}$, is then computed from the bootstrapped data, and the maximum value over this interval, denoted by

$$\mathcal{M}_t^b = \max_{t \in [\tau_0, \tau_0+\tau_b-1]} (BSADF_t^b), \quad (15)$$

is recorded.

4. This process is repeated B times to generate a distribution of bootstrapped maximum statistics. The number of bootstrap repetitions, denoted by B , must be large enough to ensure reliable critical value estimation. Based on Shi et al. (2020), we set $B = 499$ to balance computational cost and accuracy appropriately.
5. The critical values, $c_{r_2}^\beta$, are calculated as the $100(1-\beta)\%$ quantile of the sequence $\{\mathcal{M}_t^b\}_{b=1}^B$.

The parameter values used for the real-time monitoring procedure are reported in Table 2 for those that vary with sample size, and in Table 3 for those that do not. These choices influence the performance of the PS procedure and the set of bubbles it detects. To assess the robustness of our results, we perform a series of sensitivity analyses—detailed in Appendix A.1 – varying the minimum window size, sample size, lag order, and the number of bootstrap replications.

3.2. Abnormal trading activity detection

We now turn to the methodology for detecting abnormal trading activity in EUA futures and options prices. According to Chesney et al. (2015), a trade must meet three criteria to be classified as abnormal: an unusually large increase in open interest relative to trading volume, large gains and abnormal returns, and it is not made for hedging purposes. In our context, we focus on the first two criteria. Calculating hedging with the underlying asset requires trade-level data, which is unavailable from the EEX, as it only provides aggregated data, thus preventing an assessment of individual hedging positions.¹⁰ Below, we briefly outline each criterion.

¹⁰ When individual portfolio data is inaccessible, an alternative approach to estimate hedging status involves inferring whether unusual options trades are covered by comparing the theoretical volume of shares sold for hedging with the actual seller-initiated trading volume. However, we lack information on seller-initiated trading volume due to data limitations.

3.2.1. Increment in open interest relative to volume

The first criterion identified by Chesney et al. (2015) to classify a trade as abnormal is the increase in open interest relative to trading volume. The key intuition is that a sudden increase in open interest signals the opening of new positions, rather than mere turnover of existing contracts. This distinguishes potentially informed trades from high-volume days driven by speculative or liquidity-driven motives. At the same time, trading volume provides insight into how actively those newly created positions are exchanged on the same day. If volume is high but open interest does not change, the trades likely reflect offsetting activity (e.g., speculation or closing positions), rather than the accumulation of new positions.

By comparing the maximum change in open interest to the associated trading volume, we capture days in which large positions are opened and held, as opposed to churned. The difference between volume and open interest increment (Z_t) thus serves as a proxy for intra-day speculation versus longer-horizon positioning. We focus on the option with the largest increase in open interest to reduce noise from illiquid or inactive contracts, and to capture the most salient signal on any given day.

Starting from options, let K_t denote the set of available call options on day t , with each option k in the set denoted as $k \in K_t$. For each option, the increment in open interest, ΔOI_t^k , is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta OI_t^k = OI_t^k - OI_{t-1}^k, \quad (16)$$

where OI_t^k represents the open interest for option k on day t . The maximum increment in open interest across all options is then defined by

$$X_t = \max_{k \in K_t} \Delta OI_t^k, \quad (17)$$

which serves as a proxy for large buy orders. In contrast, high trading volumes can occur under various conditions, such as large sell orders or when the same option is frequently traded within a day. The observed increment in open interest suggests that other investors are not closing their positions, compelling the dealer or market maker to issue new options.

To further characterise these trades, let V_t denote the daily trading volume corresponding to the option that achieves the maximum increment in open interest, as defined in Eq. (17). The quantity

$$Z_t = V_t - X_t \quad (18)$$

measures how frequently the newly issued options are traded. A smaller Z_t implies that fewer new options are being exchanged on the day they are created. This indicates that the trader is not engaging in intra day speculation but rather maintaining the position in anticipation of future events (Chesney et al., 2015).

To assess whether these trades are indeed unusual, Chesney et al. (2015) define the joint historical probability of observing an increment in open interest close to the trading volume as

$$q_t = \mathbb{P}[X \geq X_t, Z \leq Z_t] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{1}_{\{X_i \geq X_t, Z_i \leq Z_t\}}, \quad (19)$$

where N is the length of the estimation window and $\mathbb{1}_{\{A\}} = 1$ if event A occurs, otherwise it equals zero. A low value of q_t indicates that the trades conducted on the day t were unusual compared to historical patterns, thus signalling potential abnormal trading activity.

When applying this methodology to futures contracts, the same approach can be used to identify trades characterised by exceptionally low values of q_t . For futures, the increment in open interest is defined as $\Delta OI_t = OI_t - OI_{t-1}$, and since only one contract (typically the front-December futures contract) is considered, the expression simplifies to $X_t = \Delta OI_t$.

3.2.2. Relative returns

The second criterion for detecting abnormal trades is the unusual pattern of relative returns in the days following the trade. To capture this characteristic, the maximum return of the contract over the next two trading weeks is calculated, providing a measure of significant price movements that may signal unusual events or information. For each day t , this maximum return is given by

$$r_t^{\max} = \max_{j=1, \dots, 10} \frac{P_{t+j} - P_t}{P_t}, \quad (20)$$

where P_t denotes the contract price on day t . An unusually high value of r_t^{\max} indicates the occurrence of significant market movements within two weeks of the trade, potentially suggesting anticipation of major events. In the case of European call options, where multiple contracts are considered, this computation is applied to the contract k_i that achieves the minimum value of q_i . This issue does not arise for futures contracts involving a single instrument.¹¹

3.2.3. Combining the criteria

Although we cannot assess the hedging purposes of each trade, we apply the two outlined criteria to detect abnormal activity. In particular, to classify futures or options trade k as abnormal, the trade must meet the criteria $k_t \in \Omega_1 \cap \Omega_2$, where Ω_1 identifies trades with an unusually large increment in open interest relative to trading volume and Ω_2 identifies trades with abnormal returns over the subsequent two weeks. The thresholds for these criteria are defined such that Ω_1 corresponds to days when $q_t \leq 5\%$, indicating unusual trading relative to recent history, while Ω_2 corresponds to days when $r_t^{\max} \geq q_{t,0.90}^{\max}$, indicating a significant event affecting returns in the near future.

4. Speculative bubbles and abnormal trading activity in the EU ETS

In this section, we address the main research questions of the paper outlined in Section 1, namely whether permit price volatility and spikes in the period from 2017 to 2022 were driven by speculative bubbles, whether there was abnormal trading activity during the same period and whether any detected bubbles coincide with regulatory announcements or policy changes. We do so by first presenting the empirical results from the real-time monitoring of EUA futures prices. We then report our findings on abnormal trading activity in both the EUA futures and options markets. Finally, we examine whether the identified periods of exuberance or abnormal trading align with, or are preceded by, significant regulatory events related to the EU ETS.

4.1. Bubbles

We apply the real-time monitoring procedure to daily prices of EUA futures over the period from 2017 to 2022. In the period considered, setting the minimum duration of a bubble to 7 days, we find seven distinct instances of explosive behaviour in the EUA futures prices, four in 2018 and three in 2021, with the last extending into the early months of 2022.¹² The speculative bubbles collectively span 154 days out of a total sample of 1521 trading days from 2017 to 2022. Fig. 8 illustrates the EUA futures price series, with the identified bubbles highlighted in the shaded areas, and Table 4 lists the start and end dates of these episodes, along with their durations.

¹¹ We do not consider realised gains, calculated through decrements in open interest relative to option exercises and the corresponding gains G_i . While this step is appropriate for American call options, which allow for early exercise, it is less relevant for European options and futures, where exercise only occurs at maturity. Consequently, for these instruments, $G_i \neq 0$ only on the maturity date, making this criterion unsuitable for our analysis.

¹² The original number of bubbles detected, without imposing the minimum duration of seven days, is illustrated in Table 9.

Table 4

Bubbles detected in EUA futures prices (2017–2022).

Start date	End date	Duration (days)
Mar. 21, 2018	Apr. 4, 2018	14
Apr. 6, 2018	Apr. 19, 2018	13
May 16, 2018	May 30, 2018	14
Aug. 20, 2018	Sept. 12, 2018	23
May 10, 2021	May 18, 2021	8
Nov. 24, 2021	Dec. 16, 2021	22
Dec. 27, 2021	Feb. 25, 2022	60

The first bubble in 2018 occurred between March 21 and April 4, followed closely by another from April 6 to April 19. A third bubble spans from May 16 to May 30, while a longer episode occurs from August 20 to September 12. In 2021, a bubble emerges from May 10 to May 18, followed by two extended periods of price exuberance from November 24 to December 16, and from December 27, 2021, to February 25, 2022. The average length of the bubbles is 22 days.

We compare our results with those of Wei et al. (2022) and Huang and Wang (2024), both of whom employ recursive unit root testing to detect speculative bubbles in the EU ETS. Wei et al. (2022) apply the Generalised Sup Augmented Dickey–Fuller (GSADF) test as proposed by Phillips et al. (2015) to EUA futures prices, as well as to emissions trading schemes in New Zealand, South Korea, and Shenzhen. For the EU ETS, they identify two prolonged bubble episodes: the first spanning from 6 January 2016 to 4 April 2017, and the second from 16 May 2017 to 11 April 2019, with the latter lasting 696 days. These episodes are attributed to European renewable energy policy shifts and anticipatory effects of the MSR. As our sample begins in 2017, we are unable to evaluate the 2016 episode, and we do not detect bubbles in 2017 – likely due to the lack of earlier data. However, for the 2018 portion of the second episode, our method—building on Phillips and Shi (2020) and incorporating the backward sup ADF (BSADF) test with wild bootstrap corrections (Harvey et al., 2016; Shi et al., 2020) – identifies a sequence of shorter, more granular speculative episodes. Specifically, we detect distinct bubbles in March–April, April, and May 2018, as well as in late summer, which together align closely with the broader interval reported by Wei et al. (2022).

Huang and Wang (2024) apply both GSADF and the Log-Periodic Power Law Singularity (LPPLS) model to identify positive and negative bubbles in the EU ETS from 2017 to 2022. Their GSADF results yield eight distinct bubbles: 7 March–2 May 2018, 9 May–14 June 2018, 18 July–13 September 2018, 20 April–20 July 2021, 26 July–19 August 2021, 20 August–19 October 2021, 20 October–1 November 2021, and 2 November 2021–1 March 2022. These intervals differ somewhat from our results. In the spring of 2018, for example, we identify two shorter bubbles of 14 and 13 days, respectively, while their method reports a single extended bubble over the March–May period. Likewise, we detect one bubble in May 2018 ending on 30 May, whereas their analysis shows a bubble continuing until 14 June. During summer 2018, they report a bubble beginning on 18 July, while we identify a shorter episode beginning 20 August and ending 12 September. Both studies do not detect any bubbles in 2019–2020. In 2021, Huang and Wang (2024) report five long bubbles spanning most of the year, whereas our method identifies three shorter episodes with more restrictive durations. These differences likely stem from the different methodologies: our implementation incorporates bootstrap-based critical values, designed to mitigate the risk of false positives. As a result, our approach may detect explosive episodes that GSADF without such corrections might flag.

In addition, Huang and Wang (2024) employ the LPPLS model, which provides a complementary perspective by capturing both positive and negative bubbles and offering predictive information on potential crash points. Their LPPLS estimates identify three positive bubbles: 23 August–1 September 2017, 5–14 September 2017, and 16 March–4 April 2018. While we do not detect any bubbles in 2017, we do

Fig. 8. Periods of explosive behaviour detected in EUA futures prices (2017–2022).

identify a bubble ending on 4 April 2018, which closely coincides with the LPPLS bubble, albeit beginning five days later in our case. They also identify a negative bubble from 20 September to 3 October 2022, which does not appear in our results. Overall, the LPPLS approach used by Huang and Wang (2024) complements our BSADF-based analysis by distinguishing between positive and negative bubbles.

4.2. Abnormal trading activity

To identify periods of abnormal trading activity, we evaluate the two criteria outlined in Section 3.2, first focusing on EUA futures and subsequently on EUA options. Although data limitations prevent us from assessing the hedging intent behind individual trades – and thus applying the third criterion typically used to identify abnormal trades – our analysis remains insightful.

4.2.1. EUA futures

To detect abnormal trading activity in EUA futures, we use ICE EUA futures prices. The results are summarised in Table 5, which presents the periods of detected abnormal trading from 2017 to 2022.

A total of 10 periods of abnormal trading activity were identified, with an average duration of 9.6 days. Some of these periods are close in time to previously identified speculative bubbles. For example, abnormal trading from March 7 to March 20, 2018, precedes the first speculative episode (March 21 to April 4, 2018). Similarly, the period from August 29 to September 6, 2018, partially overlaps with a bubble from August 20 to September 12. Abnormal trading from November 4 to November 12, 2021, also anticipates a speculative bubble between November 24 and December 16. The remaining seven detected periods of abnormal trading activity do not align closely with any identified speculative bubbles.

Table 5

Periods of abnormal trading in EUA futures detected (2017–2022).

Start date	End date	Duration (days)
Mar. 7, 2018	Mar. 20, 2018	13
May 2, 2018	May 4, 2018	2
Aug. 29, 2018	Sept. 6, 2018	8
Oct. 29, 2018	Nov. 6, 2018	8
Mar. 21, 2019	Apr. 4, 2019	14
Mar. 23, 2020	Apr. 4, 2020	12
Jun. 12, 2020	Jun. 26, 2020	14
Jan. 25, 2021	Feb. 1, 2021	7
Nov. 4, 2021	Nov. 12, 2021	8
Oct. 11, 2022	Oct. 21, 2022	10

4.2.2. EUA options

The abnormal trading detection technique was also applied to EEX European call options on EUA futures. It is important to note, however, that the characteristics of the options market between 2017 and 2022 present certain limitations. The market generally exhibited low liquidity – except in 2018 – and investor participation was inconsistent. These factors may limit the ability to draw robust conclusions regarding abnormal trading in options, though the analysis provides valuable preliminary insights into this less-studied segment of the ETS market.

The criteria for detecting abnormal trading in options were applied in the same manner as for futures, focusing on trades that met both Ω_1 and Ω_2 . The detected periods are listed in Table 6.

We identify twelve instances of abnormal trading activity in EUA options, most of which lasted only one day, with two exceptions lasting 2 and 3 days, respectively, resulting in an average duration of 1.25 days. Several instances of abnormal activity during August and September 2018 coincide with the price bubble identified for that period. Additionally, the detection of abnormal trading on May 5, 2021, may

Table 6
Periods of abnormal trading in EUA options detected (2017–2022).

Start date	End date	Duration (days)
Aug. 27, 2018	Aug. 27, 2018	1
Aug. 29, 2018	Aug. 31, 2018	2
Sept. 3, 2018	Sept. 3, 2018	1
Sept. 5, 2018	Sept. 5, 2018	1
Nov. 1, 2018	Nov. 1, 2018	1
Mar. 29, 2019	Mar. 29, 2019	1
Nov. 4, 2019	Nov. 7, 2019	3
Nov. 18, 2019	Nov. 18, 2019	1
Nov. 20, 2019	Nov. 20, 2019	1
Nov. 25, 2019	Nov. 25, 2019	1
Jun. 23, 2020	Jun. 23, 2020	1
May 5, 2021	May 5, 2021	1

Table 7
Number of regulatory events per year (2017–2022).

Year	Number
2017	13
2018	13
2019	20
2020	6
2021	10
2022	7
Average	11.5

indicate a market response ahead of the bubble observed in mid-May 2021, though this single-day observation provides limited evidence. The overall results for the options market should be interpreted with caution due to its relatively low liquidity. Nevertheless, the alignment of abnormal trading in 2018 with a period of heightened market participation supports the consistency of our findings from the futures market analysis, where speculative activity appeared to influence price dynamics.

4.3. Regulatory events

To examine the impact of regulatory events as potential drivers of speculative bubbles in the EU ETS, we assess whether these periods of exuberance coincide with significant policy or regulatory events. Previous studies, such as [Cretí and Joëts \(2017\)](#) and [Fan et al. \(2017\)](#), employ similar approaches, gathering EU ETS-related regulatory events or news from sources like the European Commission's DG CLIMA news site, the DG TREN legislative enforcement portal, and Thomson Reuters Point Carbon. Additionally, [Känzig \(2023\)](#) constructed a timeline of 126 policy announcements from the European Commission's Climate Action news archive, spanning 2005 to 2019. [Hengge et al. \(2023\)](#) subsequently extended this dataset to cover 2019–2021, adding events for these additional years.

Following their methodology, we extend this dataset further by incorporating regulatory events from the Climate Action news archive for the period 2021–2022, resulting in a full list of 47 events (see [Table 15](#) in [Appendix A.2](#) of the Appendix). Since the archive may not always include key announcements on EU ETS directives or laws, we supplement this dataset with additional regulatory events from the Official Journal of the European Union (available at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/oj/direct-access.html>), following the approach used by [Fan et al. \(2017\)](#). This search identified 22 relevant regulatory events, detailed in [Table 16](#) in [Appendix A.2](#). In total, our dataset comprises 69 regulatory events spanning 2017–2022, as summarised in [Table 7](#).

In [Table 8](#), we present the previously identified speculative bubbles and abnormal trading periods in EUA futures and options, matched where applicable with corresponding regulatory events. We include regulatory interventions that occurred at least seven days prior to the

start of the bubble or abnormal trading period, or that fall within their duration. For each regulatory event, we indicate whether it pertains to auctions, international (intl) credits, or free allocation, and whether it signals an increase, decrease, or no change in the stringency of the EU ETS (denoted as Increase, Decrease, and Neutral, respectively).

The first regulatory event temporally proximate to a period of exuberant trading is the adoption of Directive 2018/410/EU, issued on 14 March 2018, which reformed the EU ETS for Phase IV (2021–2030).¹³ The directive raised the annual linear reduction factor of the emissions cap from 1.74% to 2.2%, and it strengthened the MSR, doubling the intake rate of surplus allowances from 12% to 24% between 2019 and 2023. It also laid the groundwork for the Innovation and Modernisation Funds. These measures signalled higher regulatory stringency in the EU carbon market. The issuance date of the directive fell within an abnormal trading period in EUA futures from 7 to 20 March 2018. Two speculative bubbles followed, beginning on 21 March and 6 April, with the latter concluding on 19 April, eleven days after 8 April, when the directive formally entered into force.

A second wave of regulatory communication occurred in May 2018. On 4 May, the European Commission published updated figures on the use of international credits, providing retrospective data on the volume of Certified Emission Reductions (CERs) and Emission Reduction Units (ERUs) surrendered in previous compliance years.¹⁴ While this update carried no direct policy change, it preceded a brief abnormal futures trading period from 2 to 4 May 2018. More consequential were the announcements of 8 and 15 May. On 8 May, the Commission released the preliminary carbon leakage list for Phase IV, applying stricter thresholds on trade and emissions intensity to determine eligibility for free allocation.¹⁵ Several sectors were removed from the list, implying a significant reduction in the volume of permits they would receive at no cost in the future and thus representing a tightening of expected stringency. On 15 May, the Commission confirmed that the MSR would begin withdrawing approximately 265 million allowances from auction volumes starting in 2019, translating the surplus adjustment mechanism into concrete reductions in permit supply.¹⁶ A speculative bubble spanning 16 to 30 May followed immediately after these announcements.

A further speculative episode occurred between 20 August and 12 September 2018 and was accompanied by abnormal trading activity in both EUA futures (from 29 August to 6 September) and options (27 August, 29–31 August, and 5 September). On 30 October, the Commission amended the auctioning regulation to align Phase IV auction procedures with the revised ETS Directive.¹⁷ Although the amendment did not alter the total volume of permits to be auctioned, it established updated rules for scheduling, participation, and eligibility that reinforced the functioning of the MSR. A period of abnormal trading activity in futures began on 29 October and extended through 6 November, followed by abnormal options activity on 1 November. While we cannot exclude that abnormal trading activity included hedging and causality remains ambiguous, this cluster of trading intensity may reflect a speculative reaction to the regulatory event.

In 2019, no speculative bubbles were detected, but abnormal trading was observed in six instances. Of particular note are the events of 31 October and 8 November. On 31 October, the Commission adopted a regulation that operationalised dynamic adjustments to free allocation based on changes in industrial output, ensuring that firms facing a decline or increase in activity of at least 15% would see their permit allocation adjusted accordingly.¹⁸ While the mechanism is symmetrical,

¹³ [Directive2018/410/EU](#).

¹⁴ [Updatedinformationonexchangeandinternationalcredittuse](#).

¹⁵ [Commission'snoticeonpreliminarycarbonleakagelist](#).

¹⁶ [Newsonauctionvolumereduction](#).

¹⁷ [Commissionadoptsamendmenttoauctioningregulation](#).

¹⁸ [Adoptionofadjustmentoffreereallocationmechanism](#).

Table 8
Speculative bubbles, abnormal trading activity and regulatory events.

Start date	End date	Duration (days)	Type
2018			
Mar. 7	Mar. 20	13	Futures
Mar. 14: Establishment of MSR (Free allocation, Auction; Increase)			
Mar. 21	Apr. 4	14	Speculative bubble
Apr. 6	Apr. 19	13	Speculative bubble
Apr. 8: Establishment of MSR (Free allocation, Auction; Increase)			
May 2	May 4	2	Futures
May 4: Updated information on exc. and intl credit use (Neutral)			
May 8: Commission notice on the preliminary carbon leakage list for phase IV (Free allocation; Decrease)			
May 15: ETS MSR to start reducing auction volume by nearly 265 m. allowances (Auction; Increase)			
May 16	May 30	14	Speculative bubble
Aug. 20	Sept. 12	23	Speculative bubble
Aug. 27	Aug. 27	1	Options
Aug. 29	Aug. 31	2	Options
Aug. 29	Sept. 6	8	Futures
Sept. 5	Sept. 5	1	Options
Oct. 29	Nov. 6	8	Futures
Oct. 30: Commission adopts amendment to ETS auctioning reg. (Auction; Increase)			
Nov. 1	Nov. 1	1	Options
Nov. 6: Updated information on exchange and intl credit use (Intl credits; Neutral)			
2019			
Mar. 21	Apr. 4	14	Futures
Mar. 29	Mar. 29	1	Options
Oct. 31: Comm. adopts Reg. on adjustments to free all. due to activity level changes (Free allocation; Increase)			
Nov. 4	Nov. 7	3	Options
Nov. 8: Auctioning reg. amendment for phase 4 of the EU ETS published (Auction; Increase)			
Nov. 18	Nov. 18	1	Options
Nov. 20	Nov. 20	1	Options
Nov. 25	Nov. 25	1	Options
2020			
Mar. 23	Apr. 4	12	Futures
Jun. 12	Jun. 26	14	Futures
Jun. 23	Jun. 23	1	Options
2021			
Jan. 25	Feb. 1	7	Futures
May 5	May 5	1	Options
May 10	May 18	8	Speculative bubble
May 12: ETS MSR to reduce auction volume by over 378 million allowances (Auction; Increase)			
Nov. 4	Nov. 12	8	Futures
Nov. 24	Dec. 16	22	Speculative bubble
Dec. 15, 2021: Further 2022 auction calendars published (Auction; Neutral)			
2022			
Dec. 27, 2021	Feb. 25, 2022	60	Speculative bubble
Feb. 16: Revised 2022 auction calendar for general allowances published (Auction; Neutral)			
Oct. 11	Oct. 21	10	Futures

its primary aim was to reduce over-allocation by aligning free permits with actual activity levels, thereby reinforcing the integrity of the cap. On 8 November, the Commission finalised amendments to the auctioning regulation for Phase IV, codifying updated rules but without altering the timing or quantity of scheduled auctions.¹⁹

No major regulatory events coincided with abnormal trading in 2020. In 2021, however, the European Commission announced on 12 May that the MSR would withdraw over 378 million allowances from auctions between September 2021 and August 2022.²⁰ This followed the release of the 2019 total number of allowances in circulation, which remained well above the MSR activation threshold. The announcement came two days after the onset of an eight-day speculative bubble and may have reinforced expectations of tightening supply. A longer speculative bubble, extending from 24 November to 16 December, preceded the publication of the 2022 auction calendar on 15 December, which reaffirmed the pre-established volume and distribution of allowances.²¹

In 2022, we observe a 60-day speculative bubble – the longest in our dataset – spanning from late December 2021 to late February 2022. This period bracketed the publication of the revised 2022 auction calendar on 16 February, which, like its predecessor, confirmed but did not alter the timing or volume of auctions.²² The broader context, however, includes escalating geopolitical tensions. Beginning in late 2021, Russia's military build-up along the Ukrainian border raised concerns over gas supply disruptions. These concerns drove up gas prices, incentivised a switch to coal in power generation, and thereby increased EUA demand. At the same time, speculation mounted that the EU might soften ETS enforcement or defer auctions in response to energy affordability concerns.

Overall, our findings show the emergence of the correspondence between speculative bubbles and regulatory events that signal policy strengthening, auction volume adjustments, or auction calendar updates. While we do not perform econometric analyses to quantitatively assess the relationship between regulatory events and speculative episodes, our results indicate that these events may stimulate speculative activity, particularly in EUA futures.²³ It is important to note that speculative bubbles, i.e. temporary deviations of the price from the fundamental, differ from price breaks or more long-term price effects, which would result from a change in investors' long-term expectations regarding ETS stringency (Creté and Joëts, 2017).

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we investigate speculative activity in the EU Emissions Trading System from 2017 to 2022, a period marked by substantial price increases in EUAs, high volatility, and a rise in financial actors' participation.

Using a bubble-detection econometric model on EUA futures prices, we identify seven speculative bubbles within the analysed period, covering 154 days – around 10% of the total sample – indicating a significant degree of price deviation from fundamental factors. Additionally, we examine abnormal trading activity in both EUA futures and

options, detecting ten instances in futures and twelve in options, with four coinciding with identified speculative bubbles. We also compile a list of 69 regulatory events from 2017 to 2022, finding that six of the seven bubbles align closely with these regulatory events.

Our findings demonstrate that speculation plays a substantial role in the EU ETS, contributing to EUA prices deviating from their fundamental value. The identified bubble episodes occur with greater frequency and duration in the recent period than previously observed. While speculative activity can serve beneficial roles, such as improving liquidity, enhancing price discovery, and facilitating risk transfer, our evidence points to instances where speculation drives prices away from their fundamental values, potentially undermining the credibility of the market. This distinction between liquidity-enhancing and harmful speculation is critical. The former supports efficient markets and should not be discouraged; the latter, particularly when driven by uninformed noise trading or excessive herding around policy announcements, risks distorting incentives for regulated entities. From a policy perspective, these findings motivate several recommendations.

First, continuous market monitoring is essential, with particular attention to speculators' trading behaviour. Second, regulators may consider targeted reforms to mitigate excessive speculative pressures without undermining market efficiency. These could include enhanced transparency requirements on large positions, improved reporting of derivatives exposures, and refined classification of trader types. Finally, position limits – similar to those used in other commodity markets – could be evaluated as a tool to prevent the buildup of destabilising positions by non-compliant entities.

Policymakers should also exercise care in the design, timing, and communication of regulatory announcements. Our evidence suggests that such events often correspond to price bubbles. Greater predictability and clarity in regulation could reduce the likelihood of explosive prices.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Roberta Terranova: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Chiara Cozzarini:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Severin Reissl:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Massimo Tavoni:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Appendix A

A.1. Robustness analysis

We conduct a comprehensive robustness analysis to validate the results from the PS procedure for real-time market monitoring. This includes exploring the sensitivity of bubble detection to parameter variations, model selection criteria, and sample size.

A.1.1. Relaxing the minimum duration constraint

We begin by listing all speculative bubbles detected without imposing the minimum duration of seven days. Table 9 shows that several episodes identified under this relaxed criterion are isolated, single-day spikes.

A.1.2. Varying the lag order, the model selection criterion, and the size control window length

Next, we test the sensitivity of our results to the maximum lag order k_{\max} , the model selection criterion (AIC vs. BIC), and the size control window length τ_b . These parameters lack consensus in the literature and are frequently selected ad hoc. We test the following combinations²⁴:

¹⁹ [AmendmenttoPhaseIVauctioningregulation.](#)

²⁰ [Reductionofauctionvolume.](#)

²¹ [Publicationof2022auctioncalendar.](#)

²² [Revisionof2022auctioncalendar.](#)

²³ Future research could extend our analysis by incorporating event study methodologies to formally assess market reactions around regulatory announcements. This would enable the estimation of abnormal returns and trading volumes in narrow event windows, providing a clearer understanding of how regulatory changes affect market behaviour. Additionally, high-frequency policy news sentiment analysis could help distinguish between speculation driven by policy uncertainty and that triggered by ex-post market reactions to regulatory decisions. Together, these approaches would offer a more granular and causal interpretation of the relationship between policy communication and speculative dynamics in the EU ETS.

Fig. 9. Number of explosive behaviour days h_{tot} as a function of the length of the size control window τ_b .

Table 9
Bubbles detected without the minimum duration constraint.

Start date	End date	Duration (days)
Aug. 9, 2017	Aug. 9, 2017	0
Mar. 13, 2018	Mar. 13, 2018	0
Mar. 21, 2018	Apr. 4, 2018	14
Apr. 6, 2018	Apr. 19, 2018	13
Oct. 5, 2018	Apr. 14, 2018	4
May 16, 2018	May 30, 2018	14
Jun. 4, 2018	Jun. 7, 2018	3
Jul. 23, 2018	Jul. 23, 2018	0
Aug. 1, 2018	Aug. 1, 2018	0
Aug. 20, 2018	Sept. 12, 2018	23
Mar. 18, 2020	Mar. 18, 2020	0
May 10, 2021	May 18, 2021	8
Nov. 24, 2021	Dec. 16, 2021	22
Dec. 20, 2021	Dec. 22, 2021	2
Dec. 27, 2021	Feb. 25, 2022	60

- Maximum number of lag orders: $k_{max} = \{3, 6\}$;
- Length of the size control window: $\tau_b = \{24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84\}$;
- Model selection criterion, either AIC or BIC.

We begin by varying τ_b to identify a robust choice. This then serves as a baseline for evaluating the effects of k_{max} and the model selection criterion.

Size control window length. We examine how the total number of explosive days h_{tot} varies with the length of the size control window τ_b , across both AIC and BIC criteria and for $k_{max} \in \{3, 6\}$.

Under BIC (Fig. 9(a)), h_{tot} increases with τ_b up to 36, then declines. The decline is more pronounced when $k_{max} = 6$, stabilising around $\tau_b = 48$. For $k_{max} = 3$, the decline is more gradual, and stabilisation occurs only at $\tau_b = 72$.

Under AIC (Fig. 9(b)), h_{tot} also decreases with τ_b , but the patterns differ: for $k_{max} = 6$, the decline is sharp until $\tau_b = 48$, beyond which

²⁴ The lag orders $k_{max} = \{3; 6\}$ are used in various applications. Concerning the length of the size control window, some studies adopt the rule of thumb $\tau_0 : \tau_b = 2 : 1$, which we follow as well. Finally, both AIC and BIC are used in several papers, although BIC is the preferred criterion in most cases.

results become stable. For $k_{max} = 3$, the reduction is milder, with values largely stable from $\tau_b = 36$ to $\tau_b = 60$, followed by a modest drop at $\tau_b = 72$.

Generally, h_{tot} is lower with $k_{max} = 6$ than with $k_{max} = 3$.

These patterns suggest that AIC tends to detect longer periods of exuberance than BIC. Moreover, results become increasingly stable as τ_b grows, with diminishing returns beyond $\tau_b = 48$. This validates the commonly used rule-of-thumb ratio $\tau_b : \tau_0 = 1 : 2$.

We adopt $\tau_b = 48$ as a robust compromise: it lies at the stability threshold for most settings and avoids the increased computational cost associated with longer window lengths. The only notable exception is the BIC case with $k_{max} = 3$, where stability is reached only at $\tau_b = 72$. In this case, h_{tot} eventually converges to values similar to those observed under $k_{max} = 6$ and $\tau_b = 48$.

Overall, $\tau_b = 48$ provides a reasonable balance between robustness and computational efficiency.

Model selection criteria and maximum number of lag orders. We now compare the results obtained under AIC and BIC selection, for two alternative maximum lag orders, $k_{max} \in \{3, 6\}$. In this robustness check, we fix the size control window at $\tau_b = 48$, with one exception: in the case of BIC and $k_{max} = 3$, we use $\tau_b = 72$, the minimum required for stable results, as previously discussed. Fig. 10 visually summarises the detected bubble episodes under each specification, and Table 10 provides their durations.

The AIC criterion generally detects fewer but longer bubbles. For instance, under AIC with $k_{max} = 6$, six distinct bubbles are identified, with a total duration of 260 days. Using $k_{max} = 3$, five bubbles are found, with a total duration of 266 days, driven by two notably long episodes: one spanning 57 days (March-May 2018), and another lasting 104 days (November 2021 to February 2022). The latter episode aggregates what under $k_{max} = 6$ appears as two separate bubbles.

In contrast, BIC tends to identify a larger number of shorter, more fragmented bubbles. Under $k_{max} = 6$, seven bubbles are found, with a total of 154 days, while under $k_{max} = 3$, the count remains at seven but with a slightly longer total of 160 days. Most episodes under BIC last fewer than 30 days, with the exception of the final bubble in early 2022.

The impact of varying k_{max} under BIC is limited: the set of bubbles is nearly identical across values of k_{max} , with minor changes in durations. The only noticeable difference is the November-December 2021 bubble, which ends on December 16 under $k_{max} = 6$, but extends to December 22 under $k_{max} = 3$.

Fig. 10. Detected bubbles under different model selection criterion and maximum number of lag orders.

Table 10
Bubbles detected with AIC and BIC model selection criteria.

AIC, $k_{\max} = 6$	AIC, $k_{\max} = 3$	BIC, $k_{\max} = 6$	BIC, $k_{\max} = 3$
Mar. 8, 2018–Mar. 16, 2018 (8)	Mar. 6, 2018–May 2, 2018 (57)	Mar. 21, 2018–Apr. 4, 2018 (14)	Mar. 21, 2018–Apr. 4, 2018 (14)
Mar. 20, 2018–May 2, 2018 (43)	May 7, 2018–Jun. 13, 2018 (37)	Apr. 6, 2018–Apr. 19, 2018 (13)	Apr. 6, 2018–Apr. 19, 2018 (13)
May 7, 2018–Jun. 14, 2018 (38)	Jul. 18, 2018–Sep. 12, 2018 (56)	May 16, 2018–May 30, 2018 (14)	May 16, 2018–May 30, 2018 (14)
Jul. 18, 2018–Oct. 9, 2018 (83)	May 6, 2021–May 18, 2021 (12)	Aug. 20, 2018–Sep. 12, 2018 (23)	Aug. 20, 2018–Sep. 12, 2018 (23)
Nov. 11, 2021–Dec. 16, 2021 (28)	Nov. 16, 2021–Feb. 28, 2022 (104)	May 10, 2021–May 18, 2021 (8)	May 10, 2021–May 18, 2021 (8)
Dec. 27, 2021–Feb. 25, 2022 (60)		Nov. 24, 2021–Dec. 16, 2021 (22)	Nov. 24, 2021–Dec. 22, 2021 (28)
		Dec. 27, 2021–Feb. 25, 2022 (60)	Dec. 27, 2021–Feb. 25, 2022 (60)
Total: 260 days	Total: 266 days	Total: 154 days	Total: 160 days

Table 11
Parameters choice in psymonitor depending on the dataset size.

Subsample	Sample size	Min. wind. size	Min. bubble	Size control wind.
D_1	≈250	30	6	15
D_2	≈500	45	6	23
D_3	≈750	56	7	28
Full sample	1521	85	7	48

Table 12
Bubbles detected with annual datasets (D_1).

Dataset	Bubbles detected	Total number of exuberance days
2017	Sept. 6th 2017–Sept. 15th 2017 ($h = 9$)	$h_{\text{tot}} = 9$
2018	Oct. 29th 2018–Nov. 5th 2018 ($h = 7$)	$h_{\text{tot}} = 7$
2019	None	$h_{\text{tot}} = 0$
2020	Mar. 16th 2020–Mar. 30th 2020 ($h = 14$) Jun. 29th 2020–Jul. 8th 2020 ($h = 9$)	$h_{\text{tot}} = 23$
2021	May 10th 2021–May 17th 2021 ($h = 7$)	$h_{\text{tot}} = 7$
2022	None	$h_{\text{tot}} = 0$

Under AIC, changing k_{\max} has a more pronounced effect. As shown in Table 10, a higher lag order leads to shorter and more fragmented bubbles. Specifically, two long bubbles detected with $k_{\max} = 3$ are split into smaller intervals when $k_{\max} = 6$ is used.

Taken together, these results confirm that BIC delivers a more conservative detection of exuberance, with more but shorter episodes, and is less sensitive to the choice of lag order. AIC, by contrast, tends to identify longer periods of explosive behaviour, particularly under lower lag orders.

Table 13
Bubbles detected with bi-annual datasets (D_2).

Dataset	Bubbles detected	Total number of exuberance days
2017–2018	Mar. 6th 2018–Jun. 14th 2018 ($h = 100$) Jul. 4th 2018–Sep. 17th 2018 ($h = 75$)	$h_{\text{tot},17} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},18} = 175$
2018–2019	Aug. 22nd 2018–Aug. 31st 2018 ($h = 9$)	$h_{\text{tot},18} = 9$ $h_{\text{tot},19} = 0$
2019–2020	None	$h_{\text{tot},19} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},20} = 0$
2020–2021	May 10th 2021–May 27th 2021 ($h = 17$) Dec. 2nd 2021–Dec. 13th 2021 ($h = 11$)	$h_{\text{tot},20} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},21} = 28$
2021–2022	May 10th 2021–May 18th 2021 ($h = 8$) Nov. 24th 2021–Dec. 16th 2021 ($h = 22$) Feb. 2nd 2022–Feb. 8th 2022 ($h = 6$)	$h_{\text{tot},21} = 30$ $h_{\text{tot},22} = 6$

Table 14
Bubbles detected with tri-annual datasets (D_3).

Dataset	Bubbles detected	Total number of exuberance days
2017–2019	Mar. 20th 2018–Apr. 4th 2018 ($h = 15$) Apr. 6th 2018–Apr. 19th 2018 ($h = 13$) May 16th 2018–May 30th 2018 ($h = 14$) Aug. 20th 2018–Sept. 12th 2018 ($h = 23$)	$h_{\text{tot},17} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},18} = 65$ $h_{\text{tot},19} = 0$
2018–2020	None	$h_{\text{tot},18} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},19} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},20} = 0$
2019–2021	May 10th 2021–May 18th 2021 ($h = 8$) Nov. 24th 2021–Dec. 16th 2021 ($h = 22$)	$h_{\text{tot},19} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},20} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},21} = 30$
2020–2022	May 10th 2021–May 17th 2021 ($h = 7$) Dec. 2nd 2021–Dec. 13th 2021 ($h = 11$)	$h_{\text{tot},20} = 0$ $h_{\text{tot},21} = 18$ $h_{\text{tot},22} = 0$

Table 15
Regulatory events within the EU ETS (2017–2022).

No.	Date	Event description	Type
1	16/01/2017	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
2	24/01/2017	Commission adopts decision to implement Court ruling on the cross-sectoral correction factor	Free alloc.
3	15/02/2017	European Parliament voted in support of the revision of the ETS Directive for the period after 2021	Cap
4	27/04/2017	Climate Change Committee approves technical changes to auction rules	Auction
5	02/05/2017	Updated information on exchange and international credit use	Intl. credits
6	12/05/2017	Commission publishes first surplus indicator for ETS Market Stability Reserve	Auction
7	17/07/2017	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
8	26/07/2017	Court judgment again confirms benchmarks for free allocation of ETS allowances for 2013–2020	Free alloc.
9	06/11/2017	Updated information on exchange and international credit use	Intl. credits
10	15/01/2018	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
11	04/05/2018	Updated information on exchange and international credit use	Intl. credits
12	08/05/2018	Commission Notice on the preliminary carbon leakage list for phase IV (2021–2030)	Free alloc.
13	15/05/2018	ETS Market Stability Reserve will start by reducing auction volume by almost 265 million allowances	Auction
14	16/07/2018	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
15	30/10/2018	Commission adopts amendment to ETS auctioning regulation	Auction
16	06/11/2018	Updated information on exchange and international credit use	Intl. credits
17	05/12/2018	Poland's 2019 auctions to include some allowances not used for power sector modernisation	Auction
18	04/01/2019	Amendment to the ETS auctioning regulation	Auction
19	15/01/2019	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
20	15/02/2019	Adoption of the Delegated Decision on the carbon leakage list for 2021–2030	Free alloc.
21	23/04/2019	Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway to start auctions on the common auction platform soon	Auction
22	15/05/2019	ETS Market Stability Reserve to reduce auction volume by almost 400 million allowances	Auction
23	16/05/2019	Revised 2019 auction calendars including EEA EFTA volumes published	Auction
24	12/06/2019	Poland's 2020 auction volume to include allowances not used for power sector modernisation	Auction
25	19/06/2019	Updated information on exchange and international credit use	Intl. credits
26	11/07/2019	2020 and revised 2019 auction calendars of the common auction platform published	Auction
27	15/07/2019	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
28	28/08/2019	Commission amends ETS auctioning regulation for phase 4	Auction
29	31/10/2019	Commission adopts the Regulation on adjustments to free allocation due to activity level changes	Free alloc.
30	08/11/2019	Auctioning regulation amendment for phase 4 of the EU ETS published and to enter into force	Auction
31	12/12/2019	The start of auctioning for the Innovation Fund slightly postponed but no delay to the launch of the Innovation Fund	Auction
32	15/01/2020	Commission publishes status update for New Entrants' Reserve	Free alloc.
33	08/05/2020	Updated information on exchange and international credit use in the EU ETS	Intl. credits
34	08/05/2020	ETS Market Stability Reserve to reduce auction volume by over 330 million allowances between September 2020 and August 2021	Auction
35	11/12/2020	Further information on the start of phase 4 of the EU ETS in 2021: emission allowances to be issued for aircraft operators and the Market Stability Reserve	Cap
36	15/03/2021	Adoption of the Regulation determining benchmark values for free allocation for the period 2021–2025	Free alloc.
37	12/05/2021	ETS Market Stability Reserve to reduce auction volume by over 378 million allowances between September 2021 and August 2022	Auction
38	25/05/2021	Updated information on exchange and international credits' use in the EU ETS	Intl. credits
39	31/05/2021	Commission adopts the uniform cross-sectoral correction factor to be applied to free allocation for 2021 to 2025 in EU ETS	Free alloc.

(continued on next page)

Table 15 (continued).

Additional regulatory events identified by the authors of this paper			
40	29/06/2021	Commission publishes the national allocation tables of Member States for EU ETS stationary installations eligible to receive free allocation in the period 2021–2025	Free alloc.
41	22/07/2021	Revised 2021 and 2022 auction calendars published	Auction
42	15/12/2021	Further 2022 auction calendars published	Auction
43	16/02/2022	Revised 2022 auction calendar for general allowances published	Auction
44	12/05/2022	ETS Market Stability Reserve to reduce auction volume by over 347 million allowances between September 2022 and August 2023 (update)	Auction
45	12/05/2022	Forthcoming publication of the annual surplus indicator (total number of allowances in circulation) for the EU ETS Market Stability Reserve	Auction
46	19/05/2022	Revised 2022 auction calendar for general allowances published	Auction
47	28/07/2022	Revised 2022 and 2023 auction calendars published	Auction

A.1.3. Varying the sample size

To examine sensitivity to sample length, we apply the procedure to annual, bi-annual, and tri-annual sub-samples between 2017 and 2022. The corresponding collections of subsamples, denoted by D_i are defined as follows:

- $D_1 = \{\{2017\}, \{2018\}, \{2019\}, \{2020\}, \{2021\}, \{2022\}\}$
- $D_2 = \{\{2017, 2018\}, \{2018, 2019\}, \{2019, 2020\}, \{2020, 2021\}, \{2021, 2022\}\}$
- $D_3 = \{\{2017, 2018, 2019\}, \{2018, 2019, 2020\}, \{2019, 2020, 2021\}, \{2020, 2021, 2022\}\}$.

Table 11 shows the corresponding parameter settings for each case.

Annual sub-samples. Table 12 shows the bubbles detected using annual sub-samples. Annual datasets yield limited consistency with the full-sample results (Table 4). Only the May 2021 episode is consistently detected. The 2017 and 2020 sub-samples identify unique bubbles not present in the full sample, while 2018 and 2022 detect only weak or no signals. No bubbles are found in 2019, consistent with the full sample results. The short time span of annual samples ($T \approx 250$) likely impairs statistical power, particularly in detecting longer exuberance patterns.

Bi-annual sub-samples. Table 13 illustrates the results for the bi-annual samples. These are more aligned with the full-sample benchmark. In particular, the 2017–2018 sub-sample identifies two prolonged periods of exuberance in 2018, corresponding to the four shorter episodes detected in the full sample that year. This suggests some trade-off between precision and detection power: bi-annual windows capture aggregate periods well but fail to isolate finer bubble structures.

The 2018–2019 sub-sample fails to detect the early 2018 bubbles, likely due to the absence of pre-2018 observations, which are critical to identifying the start of explosive behaviour. This again highlights the importance of historical data for robust bubble detection.

The 2021–2022 sub-sample performs strongly, recovering all three bubbles from the full sample: May 2021, November–December 2021, and early 2022. While the February 2022 episode is shorter (6 days) than its full-sample counterpart (60 days), its presence confirms the robustness of the event.

Tri-annual sub-samples. Table 14 presents the bubbles detected with the tri-annual samples, which deliver the closest match to full-sample results. The 2017–2019 sub-sample identifies all four bubbles observed in 2018 in both timing and duration. The 2019–2021 window detects the May and November–December 2021 bubbles with high fidelity. Similarly, the 2020–2022 sub-sample captures these 2021 episodes as well, although the early 2022 bubble appears only partially.

The only notable deviation arises in the 2018–2020 sub-sample, which detects no exuberance despite 2018 containing multiple events.

This again points to the loss of pre-bubble information due to truncation of the early sample window.

In conclusion, this robustness analysis highlights that while parameter settings and sample sizes influence the granularity and length of detected bubbles, the core temporal structure of exuberance episodes is relatively stable.

A.2. Regulatory events

Table 15 shows the EU-ETS regulatory events, classified as either related to Auction, Free allocation, or Initial credits. Events spanning 01/01/2017 to 31/12/2018 are sourced from Känzig (2023), while those from 01/01/2019 to 31/05/2021 are from Hengge et al. (2023). Events from 01/06/2021 to the end of 2022 were manually collected by the authors of this paper using the EU Climate Action news portal²⁵ with the keywords ‘free allocation’, ‘auction’, or ‘initial credits’ focusing on relevant regulatory announcements.²⁶

In addition, we present a list of regulatory events sourced from the EU legislation portal <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/advanced-search-form.html>, which encompasses directives, regulations, and other relevant documents adopted by the EU. Our search was conducted as follows: we selected ‘Treaties’, ‘Legal acts’, ‘Consolidated texts’, ‘Lawmaking procedures’ and ‘National transposition’, and filtered by document date (01/01/2017 to 31/12/2022). We further refined the search by specifying results with ‘2003/87’ (which is the original EU Directive establishing the EU Emission Trading System) in the title and the terms ‘allocation’, ‘auction’, ‘free allowance’ within the text. The search, limited to English, yielded 21 relevant results, presented in Table 16. The first column lists the title of each regulatory action as provided by the website. Each entry includes two dates: the document’s date and its date of effect, as both can impact futures and options pricing. We also specify the document form and the CELEX number to aid readers in locating the original documents. The two tables present some overlapping regulatory events, although not many. The full list of regulatory events in chronological order is presented in Table 17.

Appendix B. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2025.108652>.

²⁵ https://climate.ec.europa.eu/news-your-voice/news_en.

²⁶ While searching, some entries related to the Innovation Fund were retrieved; however, only those explicitly concerning allocations were included.

Table 16
Regulatory events.

Title	Date of doc.	Date of effect	Form	CELEX number
COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2017/1902 amending Commission Regulation (EU) No 1031/2010 to align the auctioning of allowances with Decision (EU) 2015/1814 of the European Parliament and of the Council and to list an auction platform to be appointed by the United Kingdom	2017-10-18			
Commission Regulation (EU) No 1031/2010 of 12 November 2010 on the timing, administration and other aspects of auctioning of greenhouse gas emission allowances pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowances trading within the Community	2017-11-08	2017-11-08	Consolidated text	02010R1031-20171108
Regulation (EU) 2017/2392 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2017 amending Directive 2003/87/EC to continue current limitations of scope for aviation activities and to prepare to implement a global market-based measure from 2021	2017-12-13	2017-12-29	Regulation	32017R2392
Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC	2017-12-29	2017-12-29	Consolidated text	02003L0087-20171229
Commission Regulation (EU) No 389/2013 of 2 May 2013 establishing a Union Registry pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, Decisions No 280/2004/EC and No 406/2009/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Commission Regulations (EU) No 920/2010 and No 1193/2011	2018-01-01	2018-01-01	Consolidated text	02013R0389-20180101
Directive (EU) 2018/410 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 March 2018 amending Directive 2003/87/EC to enhance cost-effective emission reductions and low-carbon investments, and Decision (EU) 2015/1814	2018-03-14	2018-04-08	Directive	32018L0410
Decision (EU) 2015/1814 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 October 2015 concerning the establishment and operation of a market stability reserve for the Union greenhouse gas emission trading scheme and amending Directive 2003/87/EC	2018-04-08	2018-04-08	Consolidated text	02015D1814-20180408
Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC	2018-04-08	2018-04-08	Consolidated text	02003L0087-20180408
Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/331 of 19 December 2018 determining transitional Union-wide rules for harmonised free allocation of emission allowances pursuant to Article 10a of Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council	2018-12-19	2019-02-28	Delegated regulation	32019R0331
Commission Regulation (EU) No 1031/2010 of 12 November 2010 on the timing, administration and other aspects of auctioning of greenhouse gas emission allowances pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowances trading within the Community	2019-01-05	2019-01-05	Consolidated text	02010R1031-20190105
Commission Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/708 of 15 February 2019 supplementing Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the determination of sectors and subsectors deemed at risk of carbon leakage for the period 2021 to 2030	2019-02-15	2021-01-01, 2019-05-09	Delegated decision	32019D0708
Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/1122 of 12 March 2019 supplementing Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the functioning of the Union Registry	2019-03-12	2019-07-22, 2021-01-01	Delegated regulation	32019R1122
Commission Regulation (EU) No 389/2013 of 2 May 2013 establishing a Union Registry pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, Decisions No 280/2004/EC and No 406/2009/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Commission Regulations (EU) No 920/2010 and No 1193/2011	2019-03-15	2019-03-15	Consolidated text	02013R0389-20190315
Commission Regulation (EU) No 389/2013 of 2 May 2013 establishing a Union Registry pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, Decisions No 280/2004/EC and No 406/2009/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Commission Regulations (EU) No 920/2010 and No 1193/2011	2019-07-22	2019-07-22	Consolidated text	02013R0389-20190722

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Table 16 (continued).

Commission Regulation (EU) No 1031/2010 of 12 November 2010 on the timing, administration and other aspects of auctioning of greenhouse gas emission allowances pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowances trading within the Union	2019-11-28	2019-11-28	Consolidated text	02010R1031-20191128
Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC	2020-01-01	2020-01-01	Consolidated text	02003L0087-20200101
Commission Regulation (EU) No 389/2013 of 2 May 2013 establishing a Union Registry pursuant to Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, Decisions No 280/2004/EC and No 406/2009/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Commission Regulations (EU) No 920/2010 and No 1193/2011	2020-12-14	2020-12-14	Consolidated text	02013R0389-20201214
Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/1122 of 12 March 2019 supplementing Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the functioning of the Union Registry	2021-01-01	2021-01-01	Consolidated text	02019R1122-20210101
Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC	2021-01-01	2021-01-01	Consolidated text	02003L0087-20210101
Commission Decision (EU) 2021/355 of 25 February 2021 concerning national implementation measures for the transitional free allocation of greenhouse gas emission allowances in accordance with Article 11(3) of Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (notified under document C(2021) 1215)	2021-02-25	2021-02-26	Decision	32021D0355
Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/919 of 8 June 2022 amending Commission Decision 2005/381/EC as regards the questionnaire for reporting on the application of Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (notified under document C(2022) 3604)	2022-06-08	2022-06-14	Implementing decision	32022D0919
Commission Decision of 4 May 2005 establishing a questionnaire for reporting on the application of Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC (notified under document number C(2005) 1359) (Text with EEA relevance) (2005/381/EC)	2022-06-14	2022-06-14	Consolidated text	02005D0381-20220614

Table 17

Chronological overview of EU emissions trading system regulatory events.

Title/Description	Document date	Effect date	Mechanism	Stringency effect	Source
Dec. (EU) 2005/381 – Reporting on Directive 2003/87/EC	–	2017-01-16	Monitoring	Neutral	EU legislation portal
New Entrants' Reserve status update	–	2017-01-16	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Court ruling on cross-sectoral correction factor	–	2017-01-24	Free allocation	Increase	EU legislation portal
EP supports ETS revision post-2021	–	2017-02-15	Cap	Increase	EU legislation portal
Auction rule technical changes	–	2017-04-27	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Updated info on international credit use	–	2017-05-02	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Surplus indicator published (MSR)	–	2017-05-12	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
New Entrants' Reserve update	–	2017-07-17	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Court confirms allocation benchmarks	–	2017-07-26	Free allocation	Increase	EU legislation portal
Reg. (EU) 2017/1902 – Align auctions with MSR	2017-10-18	2017-10-18	Auction	Increase	EU climate action news
Reg. (EU) 1031/2010 – Auction framework	2017-11-08	2017-11-08	Auction	Neutral	EU climate action news
Intl. credit info update	–	2017-11-06	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Reg. (EU) 2017/2392 – Aviation scope limitation	2017-12-13	2017-12-29	International credits/Cap coverage	Decrease (slightly)	EU climate action news
Dir. 2003/87/EC (update)	2017-12-29	2017-12-29	All	Neutral	EU climate action news
Reg. (EU) 389/2013 – Union Registry	2018-01-01	2018-01-01	Infrastructure (all mechanisms)	Neutral	EU climate action news
New Entrants' Reserve update	–	2018-01-15	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Dir. (EU) 2018/410 – Phase 4 reform	2018-03-14	2018-04-08	Free allocation, Auction	Increase	EU climate action news
Decision (EU) 2015/1814 – Establish MSR	2018-04-08	2018-04-08	Auction	Increase	EU climate action news
Dir. 2003/87/EC (update)	2018-04-08	2018-04-08	All	Neutral	EU climate action news
Intl. credit info update	–	2018-05-04	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Preliminary carbon leakage list (Phase IV)	–	2018-05-08	Free allocation	Decrease	EU legislation portal

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Table 17 (continued).

MSR to reduce auctions by 265 million	–	2018-05-15	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
New Entrants' Reserve update	–	2018-07-16	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Amendment to auction regulation	–	2018-10-30	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Intl. credit info update	–	2018-11-06	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Poland to auction unused modernisation allowances	–	2018-12-05	Auction	Decrease	EU legislation portal
Del. Reg. (EU) 2019/331 – Harmonised free allocation rules	2018-12-19	2019-02-28	Free allocation	Increase	EU climate action news
Auction regulation amendment	–	2019-01-04	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Reg. (EU) 1031/2010 (update)	2019-01-05	2019-01-05	Auction	Neutral	EU climate action news
New Entrants' Reserve update	–	2019-01-15	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Del. Dec. (EU) 2019/708 – Carbon leakage list 2021-2030	2019-02-15	2019-05-09	Free allocation	Decrease (partial)	EU climate action news
Carbon leakage list for 2021-2030	–	2019-02-15	Free allocation	Decrease	EU legislation portal
Reg. (EU) 389/2013 – Union Registry (update)	2019-03-15	2019-03-15	Infrastructure	Neutral	EU climate action news
EEA countries join common auction platform	–	2019-04-23	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
MSR to reduce auctions by 400 million	–	2019-05-15	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Revised 2019 auction calendars incl. EEA	–	2019-05-16	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Poland's 2020 auctions incl. unused allowances	–	2019-06-12	Auction	Decrease	EU legislation portal
Intl. credit info update	–	2019-06-19	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Del. Reg. (EU) 2019/1122 – Functioning of the Union Registry	2019-03-12	2019-07-22	Infrastructure (All mechanisms)	Neutral	EU climate action news
Reg. (EU) 389/2013 – Union Registry (update)	2019-07-22	2019-07-22	Infrastructure	Neutral	EU climate action news
Revised auction calendars	–	2019-07-11	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
New Entrants' Reserve update	–	2019-07-15	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Auction regulation amendment (Phase 4)	–	2019-08-28	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Regulation on allocation adjustments	–	2019-10-31	Free allocation	Increase	EU legislation portal
Auctioning regulation for Phase 4	–	2019-11-08	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Reg. (EU) 1031/2010 (Consolidated 2019)	2019-11-28	2019-11-28	Auction	Neutral	EU climate action news
Innovation Fund auctioning slightly delayed	–	2019-12-12	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
New Entrants' Reserve update	–	2020-01-15	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Dir. 2003/87/EC (Consolidated 2020 and 2021)	2020-01-01	2020-01-01	All	Neutral	EU climate action news
Intl. credit info update	–	2020-05-08	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
MSR to reduce auctions by 330M	–	2020-05-08	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Reg. (EU) 389/2013 – Union Registry (update)	2020-12-14	2020-12-14	Infrastructure	Neutral	EU climate action news
Info on Phase 4 launch (incl. MSR, aviation)	–	2020-12-11	Cap	Increase	EU legislation portal
Dir. 2003/87/EC (Consolidated 2020 and 2021)	2021-01-01	2021-01-01	All	Neutral	EU climate action news
Del. Dec. (EU) 2019/708 – Carbon leakage list 2021-2030	2019-02-15	2021-01-01	Free allocation	Decrease (partial)	EU climate action news
Del. Reg. (EU) 2019/1122 – Functioning of the Union Registry	2019-03-12	2021-01-01	Infrastructure (All mechanisms)	Neutral	EU climate action news
Dec. (EU) 2021/355 – Transitional free allocation NIMs	2021-02-25	2021-02-26	Free allocation	Increase	EU climate action news
Benchmark values for 2021-2025 free allocation	–	2021-03-15	Free allocation	Increase	EU legislation portal
MSR to reduce auctions by 378M	–	2021-05-12	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Intl. credit info update	–	2021-05-25	International credits	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Cross-sectoral correction factor for 2021-25	–	2021-05-31	Free allocation	Increase	EU legislation portal
National allocation tables published	–	2021-06-29	Free allocation	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Revised 2021-2022 auction calendars	–	2021-07-22	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Further 2022 auction calendars	–	2021-12-15	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Revised 2022 auction calendar	–	2022-02-16	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
MSR to reduce auctions by 347M	–	2022-05-12	Auction	Increase	EU legislation portal
Announcement of new surplus indicator	–	2022-05-12	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Revised 2022 auction calendar	–	2022-05-19	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal
Impl. Dec. (EU) 2022/919 – Reporting questionnaire (update)	2022-06-08	2022-06-14	Administrative/Monitoring	Neutral	EU climate action news
Dec. (EU) 2005/381 – Reporting on Directive 2003/87/EC	–	2022-06-14	Monitoring	Neutral	EU climate action news
Revised 2022-2023 auction calendars	–	2022-07-28	Auction	Neutral	EU legislation portal

References

- Chesney, M., Cramer, R., Mancini, L., 2015. Detecting abnormal trading activities in option markets. *J. Empir. Financ.* 33, 263–275. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jempfin.2015.03.008>.
- Algieri, B., Leccadito, A., 2019. Price volatility and speculative activities in futures commodity markets: A combination of combinations of p-values test. *J. Commod. Mark.* 13, 40–54. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomm.2018.05.008>.
- Batten, J.A., Maddox, G.E., Young, M.R., 2021. Does weather, or energy prices, affect carbon prices? *Energy Econ.* 96, 105016. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2020.105016>.
- Creté, A., Joëts, M., 2017. Multiple bubbles in the European Union Emission trading scheme. *Energy Policy* 107, 119–130. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.04.018>.
- Creté, A., Jouvét, P.-A., Mignon, V., 2012. Carbon price drivers: Phase I versus Phase II equilibrium? *Energy Econ.* 34, 327–334. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2011.11.001>.

- Deeney, P., Cummins, M., Dowling, M., Smeaton, A.F., 2016. Influences from the European Parliament on EU emissions prices. *Energy Policy* 88, 561–572. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.06.026>.
- Diba, B.T., Grossman, H.I., 1988. Explosive rational bubbles in stock prices? *Am. Econ. Rev.* 78, 520–530. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1809149>.
- Dickey, D.A., Fuller, W.A., 1979. Distribution of the estimators for autoregressive time series with a unit root. *J. Amer. Statist. Assoc.* 74, 427–431. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2286348>.
- Dorn, D., Huberman, G., 2010. Preferred Risk Habitat of Individual Investors. *J. Financ. Econ.* 97, 155–173. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2010.03.013>.
- Etienne, X.L., Irwin, S.H., Garcia, P., 2014. Bubbles in food commodity markets: Four decades of evidence. *J. Int. Money Financ.* 42, 129–155. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2013.08.008>.
- Fan, Y., Jia, J.-J., Wang, X., Xu, J.-H., 2017. What policy adjustments in the EU ETS truly affected the carbon prices? *Energy Policy* 103, 145–164. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.01.008>.
- Friedrich, M., Fries, S., Pahle, M., Edenhofer, O., 2020. Understanding the explosive trend in EU ETS prices - fundamentals or speculation?. <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1906.10572>, ArXiv.Org.
- Gonçalves, S., Kilian, L., 2004. Bootstrapping autoregressions with conditional heteroskedasticity of unknown form. *J. Econometrics* 123, 89–120. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeconom.2003.10.030>.
- Harvey, D., Leybourne, S., Sollis, R., Taylor, R., 2016. Tests for explosive financial bubbles in the presence of non-stationary volatility. *J. Empir. Financ.* 38, 548–574. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jempfin.2015.09.002>.
- Hengge, M., Panizza, U., Varghese, R., 2023. Carbon Policy Surprises and Stock Returns: Signals from Financial Markets. *IMF Working Paper*, 2023/013.
- Hitzemann, S., Uhrig-Homburg, M., Ehrhart, K.-M., 2015. Emission permits and the announcement of realized emissions: Price impact, trading volume, and volatilities. *Energy Econ.* 51, 560–569. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2015.07.007>.
- Huang, W., Wang, Y., 2024. Identifying price bubbles in global carbon markets: Evidence from the SADF test, GSADF test and LPPLS method. *Energy Econ.* 134, 107626. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.107626>.
- Känzig, D.R., 2023. The Unequal Economic Consequences of Carbon Pricing. NBER Working Paper, 31221, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3386/w31221>.
- Koch, N., Fuss, S., Grosjean, G., Edenhofer, O., 2014. Causes of the EU ETS price drop: Recession, CDM, renewable policies or a bit of everything? — New evidence. *Energy Policy* 73, 676–685. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2014.06.024>.
- Koch, N., Grosjean, G., Fuss, S., Edenhofer, O., 2016. Politics matters: Regulatory events as catalysts for price formation under cap-and-trade. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 78, 121–139. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2016.03.004>.
- Kumar, A., 2009. Who gambles in the stock market? *J. Financ.* 64, 1889–1933. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6261.2009.01483.x>.
- Lovcha, Y., Perez-Laborda, A., Sikora, I., 2022. The determinants of CO2 prices in the EU emission trading system. *Appl. Energy* 305, 117903. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117903>.
- Lutz, B., Pigorsch, U., Rotfuß, W., 2013. Nonlinearity in cap-and-trade systems: The EUA price and its fundamentals. *Energy Econ.* 40, 222–232. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2013.05.022>.
- Montgomery, W.D., 1972. Markets in licenses and efficient pollution control programs. *J. Econom. Theory* 5, 395–418. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0022-0531\(72\)90049-X](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0022-0531(72)90049-X).
- Neuhoff, K., Acworth, W., Betz, R., Burtraw, D., Cludius, J., Fell, H., Hepburn, C., Holt, C., Jotzo, F., Kollenberg, S., Landis, F., Salant, S., Schopp, A., Taschini, L., Trotignon, R., 2015. Is a market stability reserve likely to improve the functioning of the EU ets? Evidence from a model comparison exercise. *Clim. Strat. Res. Rep.*
- Phillips, P.C., Shi, S., 2020. Chapter 2 - Real time monitoring of asset markets: Bubbles and crises. In: Vinod, H., Rao, C.R. (Eds.), *Financial, Macro and Micro Econometrics using R*. In: *Handbook of Statistics*, Vol. 42, Elsevier, pp. 61–80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/bs.host.2018.12.002>.
- Phillips, P.C., Shi, S., Caspi, I., 2018. Real-Time Monitoring of Bubbles: The S&P 500. <https://github.com/itamarcaspi/psymonitor>, Psymonitor R Package Version 0. 0. 2.
- Phillips, P.C.B., Shi, S., Yu, J., 2015. Testing for multiple bubbles: Historical episodes of exuberance and collapse in the S&P 500. *Internat. Econom. Rev.* 56, 1043–1078. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/iere.12132>.
- Phillips, P.C.B., Wu, Y., Yu, J., 2011. Explosive Behaviour in the 1990s NASDAQ: When did exuberance escalate asset values? *Internat. Econom. Rev.* 52 (1), 201–226. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2354.2010.00625.x>.
- Phillips, P.C.B., Yu, J., 2011. Dating the timeline of financial bubbles during the subprime crisis. *Quant. Econ.* 2 (3), 455–491. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3982/QE82>.
- Quemin, S., Pahle, M., 2022. Financials threaten to undermine the functioning of emissions markets. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 13, 1–10. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01560-w>.
- Remes, P., Ollikainen, M., Toppinen, A., 2013. Price determination in the EU ETS market: Theory and econometric analysis with market fundamentals. *Energy Econ.* 36, 380–395. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2012.09.009>.
- Rickels, W., Görlich, D., Peterson, S., 2015. Explaining European emission allowance price dynamics: Evidence from phase II. *Ger. Econ. Rev.* 16, 181–202. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/geer.12045>.
- Roques, F., Duquesne, G., Bourcier, F., 2022. Impact of Financial Actors on the European Carbon Market and Potential Measures to Stabilise Prices. *Compass Lexecon Policy Report*.
- Rubin, J., 1996. A model of intertemporal emission trading, banking, and borrowing. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 31, 269–286. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jeem.1996.0044>.
- Salvagnin, C., Glielmo, A., De Giulii, M.E., Mira, A., 2024. Investigating the price determinants of the European Emission trading system: a non-parametric approach. *Quant. Finance* 24 (10), 1529–1544. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14697688.2024.2407895>.
- Shi, S., Hurn, S., Phillips, P.C., 2020. Causal change detection in possibly integrated systems: Revisiting the money–income relationship. *J. Financ. Econ.* 18, 158–180. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/jfinec/nbz004>.
- Wegener, C., Kruse-Becher, R., Klein, T., 2024. EU ETS market expectations and rational bubbles. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848176>, Available at SSRN.
- Wei, Y., Li, Y., Wang, Z., 2022. Multiple price bubbles in global major emission trading schemes: Evidence from European Union, New Zealand, South Korea and China. *Energy Econ.* 113, 106232. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2022.106232>.